

AWARE2ALL

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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Dissemination level

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Peer review

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About AWARE2ALL

Facing to the challenge of future highly automated vehicles, where occupants can freely orient themselves to engage in non-driving activities. This new environment prompts questions about how car occupants will actually sit, what activities they will engage in, and how they will be informed through the HMI to keep them in the loop if necessary.

AWARE2ALL aims to pave the way towards Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) deployment in traffic, by effectively addressing the changes in road safety and changes in the interaction of different road users caused by the emergence of HAV through the development of innovative technologies along with the corresponding assessment tools and methodologies.

AWARE2ALL will develop safety and HMI systems that will be interrelated through achieving a holistic understanding of the scene to ensure safe operation of the HAV. AITHENA proposes a common conceptual universal safety framework for considering Human Machine Interaction (HMI). The project will be built on the results of projects funded under H2020 and other R&D programmes addressing the identification of new safety-critical situations and the most likely positions and postures considering the expected HAV applications.

The main objective of AWARE2ALL is to address the new safety challenges posed by the introduction of HAVs in mixed road traffic, through the development of inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI (interior and exterior) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety.

AWARE2ALL includes 16 partners from 6 EU Member States (ES, DE, GR, NL, FR and SE) and 2 associated countries (TR, CS) and it is complemented by the International Advisory Board (IAB) representing key stakeholders that covers the full research and industrial development automotive value chain, more specifically in the CCAM field.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
Acronyms.....	6
1. Introduction.....	7
1.1. Purpose of the deliverable.....	8
1.2. Intended audience.....	8
2. C&D&E Objectives.....	9
3. C&D Strategy	10
4. Stakeholders	11
5. Communication & Dissemination plan	12
5.1. Core Principles	12
5.2. Branding	12
5.3. Communication Plan.....	13
5.3.1. Preliminary analysis.....	13
5.3.2. Communication activities/channels	14
5.4. Dissemination Plan	15
5.4.1. Dissemination activities/channels.....	15
5.4.2. International Cooperation	16
5.5. Distribution of tasks.....	17
5.6. Evaluation.....	18
5.6.1. Website	18
5.6.2. Social Media.....	21
5.6.3. Newsletter.....	21
5.6.4. D&C material.....	22
5.6.5. Publications	22
5.6.6. Events	23
6. Exploitation plan	25
6.1. Objectives	25

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

6.2. Methodology	26
6.2.1. Research paradigms.....	26
6.2.2. Outline process for research activity	26
6.2.3. Interview Questionnaire	27
6.2.4. Method for Data Analysis	29
6.3. AWARE2ALL exploitation strategy.....	29
6.3.1. Strategy for market take-up	29
6.3.2. Individual exploitation of results.....	30
6.4. Management of Intellectual Property	32
6.4.1. General IPR Management Procedures.....	32
6.4.2. IPR Management in AWARE2ALL.....	33
6.5. AWARE2ALL expected results	36
7. References	38
8. Appendix 1	39
9. Appendix 2	51

Executive Summary

To maximize the exploitation and the impact of the project results, the consortium is committed to follow a clear and comprehensive communication, dissemination and exploitation (C&D&E) strategy. Effective communication and dissemination, aiming to maximise the reach of the project's results will be conducted in WP6, led by CAP who will act as dissemination manager.

Communication activities will be focused on raising awareness regarding project work and results and directed to a broad audience. Dissemination will target specific audiences to enable the use and uptake of project results. Dissemination will be closely linked to the exploitation strategy of AWARE2ALL, led by VICOM, who will monitor IPR.

The present Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (C&D&E Plan) defined at M6 lists all planned dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels defined in the proposal, and matches them with target stakeholders categories and key performance indicators.

This plan will be a reference for all the AWARE2ALL consortium. The performance of the plan will be assessed each 10 months, with two follow-up deliverables (D6.4 in M16, D6.5 in M26), in which the plan will be adjusted and updated. In the final review in M36.

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
C&D&E	Communication & Dissemination & Exploitation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
Euro NCAP	European New Car Assessment Programme
HAV	Highly Automated Vehicles
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
IAB	International Advisory Board
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
WHO	World Health Organization

1. Introduction

AWARE2ALL C&D&E strategy follows a 6-step approach, considering those steps that were already taken at the proposal stage, and those that will be applied throughout the project duration and periodically assessed and reviewed (each 10 months).

Figure 1. AWARE2ALL C&D strategy.

It is of outmost relevance to understand the EC definitions for C&D&E, as explained in the Webinar session: Dissemination & Exploitation in Horizon Europe [1].

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation	
Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.	Objective
Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.	Describe and ensure results available for others to USE → focus on results only!	Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)	Focus
Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community incl. media and the broad public.	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential USE of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policymakers).	People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.	Target Audience

Figure 2. EC definition of C&D&E.

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

This first WP6 deliverable, the "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan", aims to present the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of the AWARE2ALL project, coordinated by Capgemini Engineering and developed by the whole consortium.

The main objective of this plan is to establish the communication, dissemination and exploitation guidelines and the channels through which we will show all the progress and results of AWARE2ALL. It is important to ensure that the project reaches a wide audience so that the project results can be properly utilised and exploited. This plan enables the efficient and effective communication of the project objectives and results, as well as the efficient exploitation of the project results.

The guidelines developed in this plan are addressed to the project partners themselves and to a range of stakeholders, including industry professionals, academics, and the general public. It is important to ensure the dissemination of project results to all these groups to ensure their successful exploitation. This plan will also communicate the project objectives and results to the general public to raise awareness of the project and its results.

This deliverable identifies AWARE2ALL messages to raise awareness of the project, its results and to ensure effective exploitation of the results.

1.2. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D6.1 is public. Primarily, this document is developed for members of the AWARE2ALL consortium where they will find the necessary guidelines and recommendations to communicate, disseminate and exploit the project, but anyone interested in the project and its planning is welcome to read this document.

2. C&D&E Objectives

The AWARE2ALL consortium will implement a robust C&D&E strategy to contribute to increasing the global competitiveness of the activities developed in the project. Tailored activities will be designed to make the project outcomes visible and accessible to the different target stakeholders.

The objectives of the dissemination activities will be to:

(O1) Raise awareness of project's activities, outputs and benefits to get social acceptance of AWARE2ALL solutions and encourage willingness to make use of project results.

(O2) Promote new knowledge and results regarding future safety in mixed traffic scenarios and effects of diversity of users.

(O3) Join efforts, minimize duplication, maximize potential with other research initiatives.

(O4) Pave the way for successful commercial exploitation of project results in the automotive sector.

(O5) Disseminate fundamental knowledge, methodologies and technologies developed for future research activities.

(O6) Contribute to the definition of new standards, regulations, and assessment protocols.

(O7) Maximize the valorisation and exploitation of the project results.

3. C&D Strategy

Communication and Dissemination strategy in AWARE2ALL will be implemented during the project execution and is structured in three phases:

- (a) **Awareness building phase** (making the project known): to raise awareness on the AWARE2ALL motivation and reasoning behind the project, as well as objectives and initial results. M1-M6
- (b) **Participation phase** (targeting defined user groups): to let identified target groups understand the concepts of AWARE2ALL and the achieved results. In this phase, presentations and examples will be disseminated through the portal and selected events. M6-M30
- (c) **Action phase** (influencing practices, products and standards): to receive feedback in the form of demonstration of the results, alternative approaches or new reference implementations. This phase will include events with the end users, gathering final requirements for AWARE2ALL, etc. M30-M36

4. Stakeholders

The activities performed in AWARE2ALL will impact and be impacted by a wide range of stakeholders from the automotive, mobility and road safety domains. All these stakeholders are related to the project activities either directly or indirectly; C&D activities will be oriented to raise their awareness and facilitate access to the project results, considering their interests and influence to maximize the impact.

The identified stakeholders, who will be the target audience for AWARE2ALL (Figure 3) are the following:

- **Industry (IND):** It is needed to raise awareness from OEMs and TIER1s to ensure the market uptake of AWARE2ALL results (industrial consortium partners will help in adapting the message).
- **Standardisation Bodies (SB):** research results will provide inputs for current and future standards, paving the way to the exploitation of results.
- **End-Users (E-U):** acceptance from the different types of users to whom the project is addressed is crucial to ensure success of the measures and willingness to make use of project results, thus associations representing different groups of users will be involved in the project.
- **Regulation Bodies (RB):** Research output and demonstration results will be the base for further policy and regulation.
- **Assessment Bodies (AB):** Mainly Euro NCAP, assessment methodologies developed in the project will allow to define future safety assessment protocols and tests.
- **Research (R):** Find synergies with projects/groups in the field and allow for knowledge transfer for future research activities.

Figure 3. AWARE2ALL stakeholder groups and target audiences & influence matrix.

5. Communication & Dissemination plan

5.1. Core Principles

AWARE2ALL communication plan is based in the WHO (World Health Organisation) Strategic Communications Framework for Effective Communication since the values are very aligned. This framework includes six core principles [2] (see *Figure 4*):

- **Accessible:** AWARE2ALL identifies the most effective channels adapted to different audiences and makes communications accessible to people with disabilities.
- **Actionable:** The project will understand intended audience, in order to move them towards action.
- **Credible:** AWARE2ALL will ensure technical accuracy and will be transparent in its work.
- **Relevant:** Content and messages will be tailored to meet the needs of the audience and messages will be designed to motivate audiences' readiness to take action.
- **Timely:** Audiences will have the information they need when they need it to.
- **Understandable:** Part of the AWARE2ALL audiences are not technical experts. The project will use clear and plain language to explain the project results, will incorporate visual components and will communicating in multiple languages.

Figure 4. WHO principles for effective communications.

5.2. Branding

To maximise the impact of the C&D Plan, the project must have a consistent image and all communication and dissemination actions must have a similar style. We have made a brand manual for AWARE2ALL (see Appendix 1), including:

- Logo (usage, technical specifications, and alternatives)
- Typography
- Templates
- Style guide
- Information on EU funding

In addition, a project summary, with the most relevant information of the project is available (see Appendix 2).

5.3. Communication Plan

5.3.1. Preliminary analysis

As a starting point, being AWARE2ALL a new project with no base of audience, a preliminary analysis of the resources and channels of the consortium partners has been performed. The aim of this search is to decide which channels are the most adequate for the project, and to know how the project own channels can benefit from the partners' existing ones.

The partners' website and social media accounts have been analysed, to understand the audience that can be potentially reached through the consortium already existing communication channels, to maximise the impact of the actions planned. The results of the search are shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. AWARE2ALL partners' communication channels.

Partner	Website (visits)	Newsletter (subscribes)	LinkedIn (followers)	Twitter (followers)	Facebook (followers)	YouTube (subscribers)	Instagram (followers)
VICOM	2022: 193.813	Yes (internal)	10.359	1.313	-	1.810	132
THI	2023 so far: 230.000	No	19.342	1.731	11.801	2.650	9.494
CAP	2022: 127.452	YES (internal)	1.532.716	38.613	101.052	50.500	4.845
CERTH			16.529	999	-	28	128
TNO	-	-	105.067	3.936	14.735	4.430	3.354
FICO	2022: 487.990	Yes (internal)	51.855	1.821	6.215	498	-
CEA			197.285	-	88.700	-	-
TEC	19.800	YES (internal)	46.708	19.968	19.968	3.870	2.068
DLR	2022: 20,000	Yes, Internal: 8,127 External: 1,720 subscribers (public &	157,896	German: 108,445 English: 45,055	German: 108,445 English: 45,055	-	-

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

		press newsletter); 2,309 subscribers (R&D newsletter)					
FEKA	10.200	No	8.792	-	-	-	553
GEST			517	297	174	118	355
IRTSX	27.556 in 2022	YES and shared on LinkedIn & Twitter	5.313	3.424	3.424	567	-
SYR	2023: 410 – Jan 382 – Feb 402 – Mar 412 – Apr	YES (internal)	2.076	-	-	-	453
ESI			26.284	4.729	-	2.870	-
HUM			11.566	175	-	406	-

5.3.2. Communication activities/channels

At the proposal stage, a preliminary C&D Plan was already drafted. Based on it, channels and activities to be effectively used in AWARE2ALL have been identified and are shown below.

Table 2. AWARE2ALL communication activities/channels.

Activity/Channel	Audience (Objectives)
AWARE2ALL web (www.aware2all.eu)	All (O1, O2, O3, O5, O7)
AWARE2ALL Social Media <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn (https://www.linkedin.com/company/aware2all) • Twitter (https://twitter.com/AWARE2ALL_he) • YouTube (https://www.youtube.com/@aware2all) 	All (O1, O5)

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Press release (yearly)	All (O1, O5)
Newsletter (each 6 months, first on June 2023)	All (O1, O5, O7)
D&C material <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brochure • Rollup • Video • Summary 	All (O2, O5)
Project events	IND, E-U, R (O4, O5, O7)
EU initiatives & associations events	SB, RB, AB, IND (O1, O2, O4, O5, O6)

5.4. Dissemination Plan

5.4.1. Dissemination activities/channels

Dissemination of the project outcomes is essential because it facilitates the transfer of results and their use by a wider audience, to favour their exploitation. Communication activities are needed to reach the audience.

In AWARE2ALL, project outcomes will include tangible results, and also abstract results (knowledge, skills, and experience). The following table includes the Dissemination channels and activities that were firstly drafted at the proposal stage.

Table 3. AWARE2ALL dissemination activities/channels.

Activity/channel	Audience (Objectives)
Scientific & technical articles	R, IND (O2, O3, O5)
Presentations on conferences	R, IND (O2, O3, O5)
Workshops	All (O3, O4)
Clustering & engagement activities	IND, R (O3, O4, O5)
Project events	IND, E-U, R (O4)
EU initiatives & associations events	SB, RB, AB, IND (O1, O2, O4, O6)
Recommendations	SB, RB, AB (O1, O4, O6)
Open Research outputs	R, IND (O3, O4, O5)

The journals and conferences where AWARE2ALL results will be presented have already been identified. We are working to share efforts with each partner.

Table 4. List of journals for AWARE2ALL dissemination.

Journal	Partner(s)
Accident Analysis & Prevention	TBD

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

ETRR-European Transport Research Review	TBD
IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology	TBD
Journal of Safety Research	TBD
Safety Science	TBD
Traffic Injury Prevention	TBD
Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies	TBD
Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour	TBD
International Journal of Crashworthiness	TBD
Transportation Engineering	TBD
European Transport Research Review	TBD

Table 5. List of events for AWARE2ALL dissemination.

Event	Date	Partner(s)
HUMANIST Conference	21-22/09/2023	CERTH
EUCAD	03-04/05/2023	VICOM + CAP
ITS European Congress	22-24/05/2023	VICOM + CAP
Driving Simulation Conference	06-08/09/2023	IRTSX
IRCOBI	13-15/09/2023	TBD
11th International Congress on Transportation Research (ICTR)	20-22/09/2023	TBD
EARPA FORM Forum	17-18/10/2023	TBD
ZINC Conference	29-31/11/2023	SYR + CEA
RTR Conference	2024	TBD
Transport Research Arena (TRA)	2024	TBD
Automated Vehicles Symposium	2024	TBD
CLEPA Conference	2024	TBD
HFES International Meeting	2024	TBD
ZINC Conference	2024	SYR

These lists are expected to be very dynamic, needing continuous updates. Thus, a document containing the lists is available to all the project partners in the shared folder.

5.4.2. International Cooperation

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

AWARE2ALL has defined a task oriented to the international cooperation of the project. This task includes two main activities, that will provide an excellent opportunity to promote the project to a more diverse audience and a wider geographical coverage.

On one side, the International Advisory Board (IAB) of the project consists of external leaders of the industry, academia, standardisation organisations and public authorities. Most of them are from non-EU countries (US, Canada, Australia, Singapore and Finland). The IAB will be expanded during the project execution and will extend the visibility of the project beyond the borders of the consortium.

On the other side, AWARE2ALL will participate in twinning activities with related initiatives and projects at international level, to find synergies and potential further collaboration. This activity is allocated in task T6.2 about international cooperation. Align by the support of this activity (T6.1).

5.5. Distribution of tasks

C&D activities in AWARE2ALL is a transversal work in which all consortium partners are involved, and it will take place throughout the life of the project.

Since C&D is a relevant process of the project, the distribution of tasks has been made available to all project partners. To consolidate and monitor the execution of the different activities and channels defined for C&D, and to control their level of accomplishment and responsible partner(s), a document “C&D Activities planning” has been created and is accessible to the project partners in the Teams shared folder, within the WP6.

Figure 5. Location of the C&D managing document in the shared folder.

The document contains one sheet per natural year in which the project will be active (2022-2023-2024-2025) and the distribution is made on a week basis, with columns identifying the month of the project and the date of the week. This will allow the AWARE2ALL partners to have some time to perform the work assigned.

There are additional columns indicating the activity to be performed, the topic and the partner responsible as shown in *Figure 6 C&D Activities Planning document, 2023 view*. Figure 6.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

2023	Activity	Topic	Contributor	Sincronization
January	Summary Presentation of the Project	C&D material 6.1 + social media	CAP	T6.1
March	Post on Social Media	Social Media	CAP	8 March Woman's International Day
	Project brochure	C&D material 6.1	CAP	T6.1
	News - External workshop (main results, participants)	International cooperation + Social media + Workshop	CAP	T1.1&T6.1&T6.2
	Workshop Social media posts (invitation & Results)	Social media	CAP	D1.1 Critical scenarios
April	Project Summary Rollup	C&D Material 6.1	CAP	EUCAD Event
	Project Summary Video (Motion Graphics)	C&D Material 6.1	CAP	EUCAD Event
	DEMO Presentation Post	Social Media	CAP	DEMO's WP
	Deliverable D6.1	C&D Material 6.1	CAP	D6.1 Milestone
	Website setup and release	C&D Material 6.1	CAP	EUCAD Event
May	Website post	Social Media	CAP	Website release
	EUCAD Event Campaign	Social Media	CAP	EUCAD Event
	EUCAD + Photo on LinkedIn and Twitter	Event + Social media	CAP	EUCAD Event
	F2F San Sebastian - Video & Photos	Social media	CAP	EUCAD Event
	Blog Article	Website	CAP	Website release
June	ITS Europe Event - Paper presented	C&D Material	CAP	ITS Europe Event
	1st Newsletter	Newsletter	CAP	Website update
	Social media post	Social media	CAP	
July	Blog Article	Website	THI	
	Infographic - Use Cases defined	C&D Material	CAP	Milestone Use Cases Defined
	Update Use Cases	Website	CAP	Milestone Use Cases Defined
August	Blog Article	Website	VICOM	
	Social media post	Social media	CAP	
	Social media post	Social media	CAP	
September	Blog Article	Website	CERTH	
	Driving Simulation conference	Event + Social media	CAP	Driving Simulation Conference
	IRCOBI	Event + Social media	CAP	IRCOBI Event
	Blog Article	Website	TNO	
	ICTR	Event + Social media	CAP	ICTR Event

Figure 6 C&D Activities Planning document, 2023 view.

The activities are marked with different colours depending on the type of activity: Workshop/Event/Social Media/C&D Material/Website.

5.6. Evaluation

The evaluation of the C&D activities in AWARE2ALL is based on the Communication Evaluation Toolkit produced by the EC-Directorate General for Communication and released in 2017 [3].

For each C&D activity, a KPI has been defined per year of the project. In the deliverables D6.4 in M16 and D6.5 in M26, an evaluation of the activities will be performed according to criteria detailed below (Table 6), and adjustments and updates will be performed to make sure that the KPIs are achieved, and the impact of the project is maximised.

Note: The yearly KPIs are cumulative.

5.6.1. Website

One of the most important channels of the project is the website where all information will be shown in continuous reporting: project objectives, project partners, project progress, public deliverables, communication and dissemination material and different news around AWARE2ALL. The link to the website is as follows: www.aware2all.eu.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Figure 7. Screenshot of the project website.

The website structure is the following:

- **Home**

The homepage first shows a reel with images and video about the project. Then, a short description of the project, the partners involved in the project and the latest news and events of the project.

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- **About**

The objective is to show the motivation, objectives, methodology and demonstrators involved in the project.

- Motivation
- Objectives
- Methodology & Workplan
- Demonstrators

- **Consortium & IAB**

This page shows the participants in the project either as part of the consortium or as part of the International Advisory Board linked to their own websites. It also includes a map with the location of each partner.

- **Resources**

All public deliverables, journal publications and communication and dissemination material will be uploaded here.

- **News & Events**

The blog, news related to the project and project and promotional events will be published on this page of the website.

- **Contact + Subscribe Newsletter**

Finally, a contact form and a subscription box to the project's newsletter.

Some KPIs were already defined at the proposal stage, and some additional KPIs are set once the project has started:

Table 6 Defined KPI table for AWARE2ALL website.

Metric	Explanation	KPI		
		Y1	Y2	Y3
Visits	The number of visits (or sessions) to a website	2,000	5,000	10,000
Page Impressions	Number of pages requested	4,000	10,000	20,000
Return Visit Rate	The Return Visit Rate is calculated as the number of visits from returning visitors divided by the total number of visits to the site (loyalty of visitors)	400	1,000	2,000
Time spent per visit	The average amount of time spent per visit (indicator of interest)	30sec	30sec	60sec
Page views per visit	The average number of pages viewed per visit (indicator of interest)	3	4	6

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Bounce rate	The percentage of visits that only has one page view before exit (indicator of relevance of the content or difficulties in finding information)	40%	40%	45%
Conversion rate	The percentage of visitors that complete a defined goal (sign-up to the newsletter, download of documents)	50%	30%	20%

5.6.2. Social Media

AWARE2ALL has set up accounts in most relevant social media channels: LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube. The links to the accounts are:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/aware2all>
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/AWARE2ALL_he
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@aware2all>

Table 7 Target KPIs for social media by year.

Metric	Explanation	KPI		
		Y1	Y2	Y3
Total followers	Number of users that are following the accounts.	180	230	280
Number of posts	Content published in social media	48	96	144
Impressions	How often have posts been seen (on average for the period)	100	150	200
Engagement (Rate)	The number of times users interacted with your post divided by the number of impressions a post received (on average for the period)	20	30	40

5.6.3. Newsletter

AWARE2ALL will provide insights about the most relevant findings and information on a periodic basis through a newsletter, that will be available at the website, and will also be sent to the people that has subscribed to the newsletter.

For the newsletter sent by e-mail, we will consider the metrics of Table 8.

Table 8 Target KPIs for newsletter by year.

Metric	Explanation	KPI		
		Y1	Y2	Y3
Subscribers	The number of people subscribed to the newsletter.	25	50	100

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Unsubscribes	Number of people unsubscribing from the newsletter.	0	5	10
Open rate	The percentage of subscribers that open the newsletter.	80%	70%	65%
Forward rate	The percentage of subscribers that forward the newsletter to friends/colleagues.	5%	5%	10%
Bounce rate	The percentage of mails not delivered because of closed email accounts or error in mail address (indicator of quality of the subscribers' list)	1%	2%	5%

5.6.4. D&C material

Dissemination and communication material in AWARE2ALL will be mainly of three types:

- Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, rollups, etc.)
- Press release
- Video

All the print materials will be available in digital format and will also be used as content for social media and for the website.

Table 9 Objective results of the Dissemination and Communication materials.

Metric	Explanation	KPI		
		Y1	Y2	Y3
Material generated	The number of D&C materials prepared.	3	5	7
Number of downloads	Number of times that the material has been downloaded.	20	30	40
Material distributed	Number of elements of printed material that have been distributed in events (indicator of people interested in the project)	100	200	400

5.6.5. Publications

AWARE2ALL promotes Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and support the transparency, reproducibility, and replicability of results, thus improving the robustness of the research (higher quality science, by increasing credibility and reproducibility of research outputs) and increasing the expected impact of the project.

Scientific and technical articles, presentations on conferences, procedures, recommendations, and datasets are considered publications in AWARE2ALL.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

As part of its Open Science approach, AWARE2ALL will encourage the production of research papers in international journals all along the project duration. Publication in open journals and publications and in ORE (Open Research Europe) platform will be prioritised. Besides adoption of open access modes (e.g., Gold or Green) for all scientific papers produced, pre-prints of these papers will be shared among the partners.

Table 10 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for publications by year.

Metric	Explanation	KPI		
		Y1	Y2	Y3
Number of peer reviewed articles	Number of scientific and technical articles submitted to publications with peer-review process.	1	6	12
Number of other publications	Number of publications that are not peer reviewed articles, or that are oriented to a more general audience.	1	2	3
Presentations on conferences	Number of conferences with a paper or a session accepted.	2	5	8
Presentations in EU initiatives & associations events	Being a EU funded project, AWARE2ALL must provide content.	2	4	6
Recommendations	Number of documents containing policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy... (e.g. white paper).	0	0	3
Datasets (incl. metadata)	Snapshots of datasets that will be published via ZENODO (Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN).	0	1	2

5.6.6. Events

Events in AWARE2ALL aim to engage stakeholders (or participants) in some form. According to the objective and the stakeholders involved, there are different types of events considered in the project:

- **Workshops** – events with the aim to exchange knowledge and to collect inputs that will be of application to the project. These are private events that will be addressed to certain stakeholders according to the objective of the workshop.
- **Clustering & engagement activities** – AWARE2ALL is built over existing knowledge from previous activities, especially from finalised and on-going H2020 funded projects related to the domains addressed in the project. Taking advantage of synergies with other related initiatives will allow to advance more effectively.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

- **Project events** – addressed to industry, research and end-users, the main objective of this type of events (funded by the project) is to reach as many people as possible so they become familiar with the project results and increase the acceptance. This is a public event.
- **Meetings with stakeholders** – addressed to standardisation bodies, regulatory bodies and assessment bodies, these meetings will take place to explain the main outcomes of the project and how they can affect/influence regulations, standards and assessment methods and will be mostly private events.

Table 11 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for events by year.

Metric	Explanation	KPI		
		Y1	Y2	Y3
Number of events	Number of project events, workshops, twinning activities and meetings organised	4	8	14
Attendees	Number of people participating	40	50	60
Networked projects	Finished and ongoing research projects in the field, sharing information with AWARE2ALL	6	12	18

6. Exploitation plan

The following subsections describe the different sections of AWARE2ALL's exploitation plan. This plan is the starting point for the work to be carried out in task T6.4 Innovation management (including IPR), which starts in M07 and ends with the elaboration of D6.3 Exploitation roadmap due M36.

6.1. Objectives

In order to accomplish the objectives of AWARE2ALL, one of the steps is to develop an exploitation roadmap, based on the developed solutions identified during the project. The plan requires the review of local information, the identification of strategic stakeholders that enable the further development of the solutions and implementation in different scenarios, the identification of funding sources, and the establishment of common requirements and strategies for replicating and making sustainable the innovative solutions.

A comprehensive exploitation roadmap will be developed by the end of AWARE2ALL, considering all individual and joint results of the project, including commercial and non-commercial exploitation. During the project, we will provide more detailed information about the potential "market" for AWARE2ALL, in the very broad sense of the word:

- Areas in which we expect to make an impact.
- Needs that might be solved/met thanks to the results of AWARE2ALL.
- Where/How the outputs will be made available during and after the project.
- Who are the potential users of the results and who are the potential clients.

When preparing an exploitation plan it is common to address several mandatory issues:

1. What is the offer? The idea is to find a basic concept to exploit within the initial set of core countries that can also be adapted with only minor changes or additional information to enter new countries during the ramp-up phase.
2. What opportunities are available? To identify optimal opportunities for AWARE2ALL is another key issue. The needs of the market (or other types or needs, such as artistic, social, etc.) give the direction in order to better define what will exploit and how. It is necessary to have a global vision not only as far as commercial exploitation is concerned, but also in terms of information, contacts, etc.
3. How can we address these opportunities? The complementarities of roles between consortium members are very important for this task. This will be the objective of the next sections, as well as further versions of this deliverable.

This document will start the process of finding answers to this series of questions to ensure the successful exploitation of the AWARE2ALL results.

6.2. Methodology

A business research process will be followed during the AWARE2ALL project, using mixed methodologies, after secondary research is carried out. The following sections describe the types of research paradigms applied and the methodology to be used in AWARE2ALL.

6.2.1. Research paradigms

Paradigms, in a practical sense, are frameworks which offer a means to comprise an accepted set of theories, methods and ways of defining data. For the purpose of the present deliverable, a set of social methods (guidelines on how the researcher should carry out the research) and technical methods (the techniques adopted during the research) were decided upon to aid the research.

A phenomenological paradigm focusing on Qualitative data, and an interpretivist approach to the collection of research data was chosen as the primary research paradigm. Secondly, a positivistic paradigm was applied focusing on the interpreted qualitative research data. A positivistic approach provides richness to the research and provides insight to categorical data. The research process is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Research process

6.2.2. Outline process for research activity

The following process will be followed in the project:

1. A research question, although self-evident, was defined: **How can AWARE2ALL be exploited?**

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

2. A secondary research will be carried out to gain a current and global view of the markets and social contexts in which AWARE2ALL would be relevant.
3. A set of research hypotheses will be derived from the research question and primary research review and formulated as question (social level), see Section 6.2.3 below.
4. One or more representative from each partner will be interviewed for one hour (alternatively offline by sending a written survey) using the questionnaire (technical level). If deemed appropriate, experts external to the Consortium will also be interviewed (members of the IAB).
5. Responses will be collected using a repertory grid.
6. A post analysis will be performed on the responses in order to:
 - a. Deconstruct responses into a set of defined terms.
 - b. Identify limitations and delimitations in the responses.
 - c. Detect common trends in the responses and quantify them informally using General Analytic approach.
 - d. Interpret the analysis to draw conclusions for the next stage of the research.
7. A formal report on the interview results and conclusions will be discussed and verified by interview with the respondents.
8. A final report will be generated to form the basis for the final business and exploitation plan (D6.3 due M36).

6.2.3. Interview Questionnaire

The questions and their motives are described as follows:

1. What is AWARE2ALL (for you)?

The motive of the question is to solicit a general description of the project and its goals from the respondent and to set the tone and scope for the interview.
2. Describe the AWARE2ALL marketplace or audience in your own words?

The AWARE2ALL consortium is made up of numerous different staff and organisations all with a different perspective on both AWARE2ALL, the "markets" and social contexts it is applicable in, and on the definition of "market" in itself. The purpose of the question is to have a global view of the perception of the AWARE2ALL's target market, in the very broad sense of the word, to be later generalised and concluded as appropriate target markets for the project Results.
3. Who are the competitors and/or potential partners?

The motive of the questions is to cast a wide net and broaden the list of alternative, comparative, and substitute technologies similar in scope to AWARE2ALL. Existent and emerging companies offering similar services or technologies will be included in the scope of the question.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

4. What is the AWARE2ALL offering?

The respondents will be asked to characterise “What is AWARE2ALL?” and to describe “What does AWARE2ALL offer?”. The questions are predicated on the AWARE2ALL results being ideal and the implicit and inferred goals of the Description of Action being fully met.

5. How do people currently do “business”?

The motive of the question is to understand current workflows and process that AWARE2ALL could enhance or improve. The motive of the question is to draw a baseline description of the current need that might be satisfied by the AWARE2ALL technology, product or service.

6. What can be currently enabled, created or rationalised by AWARE2ALL?

The motive of the question is to understand, from the perspective of the project participants and their knowledge of their partners, and market trends, what innovation could be supported or created by AWARE2ALL or what current practices could be rationalised from an efficiency or cost point of view. The question also reinforces Question 5.

7. What can AWARE2ALL substitute and which are its substitutes?

The motive of the questions is to identify commercial exploitation opportunities that AWARE2ALL should target. What existing technologies, products or services could be substituted by AWARE2ALL. A second motive of the questions is to detect other emergent technologies, products or services which may present a threat to the exploitation of AWARE2ALL. The Question also reinforces Questions 3, 5 and 6.

8. What is the AWARE2ALL USP (Unique Selling Point)?

After the interviewees are asked to describe the Unique Selling Point of AWARE2ALL the question will be further simplified to “What is AWARE2ALL in 20 words?” and “Describe it to your boss’s boss or somebody you have just met”. The question also will act as a reinforcement to Question 4.

9. What could be the switching costs to or from AWARE2ALL?

The motive of the question is to approximate the scale and dimensions of switching to or from AWARE2ALL. Switching costs to AWARE2ALL are an important factor in considering the cost to adoption of AWARE2ALL and how the barrier can be reduced. Insight into the possible costs structure for AWARE2ALL exploitation and gauge options for medium term business plan, sales growth, etc. Estimation of switching cost are an important factor when deciding on pricing models and at what point AWARE2ALL exploitation should change from loss leading to profit leading. The question also reinforces questions 5 and 6.

10. Potential users, clients, sectors, and regions?

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

The motive of the question, reinforcing Questions 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7, is to identify key market segments, potential client and user types and what geographical regions AWARE2ALL would most likely be best received when exploited.

11. Barriers to adopting AWARE2ALL (opportunities)?

In addition to the switching cost and offering question in Question 5, 6 and 9, the motive of the question is to lead the interviewee in identifying potential issues in the adoption and uptake of AWARE2ALL amongst established target customers and regions in the market.

12. AWARE2ALL sales, uptake, and exploitation paths?

The motive of the question is to solicit the views of the partners and associate to the business models. As part of the interview the interviewee will be led in their responses to obtain information appropriate to Business Model Canvas technique chosen for the project. The question reinforced Questions 6, 7 and 10.

6.2.4. Method for Data Analysis

As a phenomenological approach will be used, quantification of the qualitative data will be kept to a minimum (critical incidence technique and set analysis). The main elements of the analysis are:

- A process in which a tentative analysis is undertaken at the preliminary stages of the research with this analysis being compared to new data during the research.
- Reduction of data, i.e., the sorting categorisation, prioritising data, interrelating data.
- Explaining, understanding the coherence of the subject under study and making sense of the action, goals and motives of the research so the participants can make sense of the process and results.

6.3. AWARE2ALL exploitation strategy

6.3.1. Strategy for market take-up

Given the level of technical maturity expected by the end of AWARE2ALL project, there is a clear need for additional work beyond the end of the project implementation, if AWARE2ALL technology is to make an impact on HAV safety. Thus, a three-phase exploitation plan has been devised, covering the duration of AWARE2ALL's implementation and a four-year period beyond such end. This plan is summarised below:

- Phase 1 - During AWARE2ALL (2022 – 2025). Objectives: (1) To develop the technology to achieve a TRL 5 for all expected systems; (2) to construct a roadmap for the further development of the technology (including scientific direction, further funding, and business planning); and (3) to raise awareness to various stakeholders (industry, policy makers, scientific community, public) and provide recommendations for policies and standards.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

- Phase 2 - Beyond AWARE2ALL - Industrialisation (2025 – 2027). Objectives: (1) To use the TRL 5 systems developed within Phase 1 as a base to further increase the technical maturity of the technology up to TRL 7; (2) to secure further public and/or private funding to enable these technical development activities; and (3) to collaborate with regulatory, standardisation and assessment bodies to publish policies, standards and protocols that allow the industrial deployment of AWARE2ALL technologies.
- Phase 3 - Beyond AWARE2ALL – Market deployment (2027 – 2029). Objectives: (1) To use the TRL 7 device developed in Phase 2 as a platform to increase the technical maturity of the technology up to TRL 9; and (2) establish links with major stakeholder(s) in the automotive sector with a view to bringing AWARE2ALL’s technology, or parts of it, to market by approximately 2029.

6.3.2. Individual exploitation of results

The table below include the preliminary individual exploitation plans. As the project is still in an initial stage, these will be refined and modified over the lifetime of the project when more results become available.

Table 12 AWARE2ALL main exploitation interests by partner.

RTO / ACADEMIA	
From a research perspective, AWARE2ALL will allow RTOs to meet the requirements of local companies and institutions, enhancing their competitive edge and improving society’s economic development and quality of life, via technology transfer. AWARE2ALL will also allow academic organisations to extend their expertise and roadmaps with leading-edge technological and scientific developments in a European framework.	
VICOM	1) Transfer Technology to Local and European Companies. 2) Extend the expertise in computer vision and sensor fusion with leading technology and scientific developments. 3) Maintain an active position as reference agent in Spain R&D activities in sensor fusion for the automotive domain.
THI	Integrate project results into extensive as well as practice-oriented lectures and advanced training programs, conference papers and peer-reviewed journal papers. Open new opportunities in offering research, new technology and testing services for commercial partners.
CERTH	The result of the work is targeting third party royalties to the industry. Continue and progress in various research actions in the area of road automation and C-ITS and human factors. Publish its research efforts and achievements in key scientific magazines and conferences.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

TNO	Knowledge gained within AWARE2ALL will be used to support regulatory bodies and governmental policy makers with respect to CCAM developments and regulation, as well as to serve industry with the newest state-of-the art technology.
CEA	Technology transfer to French and EU industrial partners. New Human Factors knowledge that will be used for scouting new applications, as well as for educational purposes and advance in an AVAS system that will be offered to the industry for further development and implementation.
TEC	Technology and knowledge transfer to industry in shared control techniques and Control – Actuation – Decision Making algorithms, for automated shuttle vehicles.
DLR	New methods for analysis and optimization of passive safety elements in the combination of airbags, mechanical interior structures and body in white components (with new positions). Extend the experience in CAD, FEM and optimization tools for integral safety systems.
IRTSX	Prove technological concepts on cognitive load, situation awareness and multimodal HMI design in their demonstrator, paving the way for further maturity progress towards industrial transfer.
INDUSTRY	
AWARE2ALL project involves a wide range of industrial partners, which will have the opportunity to further develop the expertise in their domain, strengthening their portfolio of products and services. Via the project, many solutions will be tested and validated shortening the way to market for industrial exploitation.	
TIER1	
FICO	Advanced software including sensor fusion and object detection/HRU attention analysis to improve performance and reliability of perception systems and its results.
FEKA	New lighting system for eHMI purposes (new line of products)
GEST	Hardware (2D and 3D interior cameras – direct sale) and software (direct sale or licensing) for: occupant classification / detection, modelling of posture and position on the seats, estimation of age, gender and size, detection and classification of other objects in the cabin.
Technology providers	

CAP	Improve engineering capabilities in multi-modal eHMI (light and sound) and testing methodologies allowing the provision of a new range of services for the automotive industry in this field.
SYRM	Strength position as a technology and service provider for next generation autonomous vehicles. Exploit the project results to further scrutinize its solutions against future use cases, as well as showcase the integrated solution as a consolidated future offering to Tier 1 and OEM business partners.
ESI	Extension of simulation capabilities in passive safety for wider variety of occupants.
HUM	HUM expect to develop/explore certain tools to assess the potential injuries and countermeasures for regulatory bodies and consumer testing agencies to adopt in future regulations and testing protocols.

6.4. Management of Intellectual Property

IPR management is a key activity in the exploitation task of AWARE2ALL. Before explaining the methodology and the different strategies to protect the IP developed in the project, it is worth highlighting some key concepts:

- **Intellectual Property (IP)** are the key assets developed during (or before) the project (i.e., ideas, design, technologies, etc.).
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** are the legal tools to support the commercial exploitation of those IPs previously identified.
- **Background IP:** Any data, know-how and/or information, both tangible and intangible, as well as any rights which are owned or controlled by a party prior to its accession to the Project (or done in parallel to the Project) and which is needed for carrying out the project by another party.
- **Foreground IP:** Any tangible or intangible output (know-how, data, information) and the right attached to them, whether protected, which is generated during the lifetime of the project.

6.4.1. General IPR Management Procedures

For the project to succeed, before its launch, all project partners agreed on explicit rules concerning ownership of intellectual property (IP), access rights to background and foreground IP, as well as the protection of intellectual property rights (IPR) and confidential information. Such issues are addressed in detail within the Consortium Agreement (CA) between all project partners.

The purpose of the Consortium Agreement is to establish a legal framework for the project to provide clear regulations for issues within the consortium related to IP Ownership, Confidential Information, Open-Source issues, Standard contributions, and Access Rights to Background

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

and Foreground IP for the duration of the project and any other matters of the consortium's interest. The AWARE2ALL consortium adopted the DESCA 2020 Model Consortium Agreement. Although the CA is a base and stable document (first version was signed before project launch), it could be modified during the project duration to consider any updated consensus on the project results. The CA also covers full rights and responsibilities of participants in respect of the confidentiality of information disclosed by the partners during the project, as well as the publication and communication of information during the project. Moreover, the CA provides additional rules to ensure smooth dissemination of the results. Settlements of internal disputes and of course Intellectual Property (IP) arrangements are part of the CA as well.

Any result generated before the effective date of the CA (i.e., background) shall remain with the respective party bringing such background to the project. Any result generated by a party after said date, during and within the scope of the project (i.e., Result) whether or not it qualifies for Intellectual Property Right (IPR) protection, shall vest in the party that generated such Results. Any jointly generated Result will be jointly owned where the rights and obligations associated to such jointly generated Result are regulated in the CA. Throughout the execution of the project, all partners will continuously contribute to the identification of Results that may qualify for IPR protection and will act with the aim of achieving a meaningful outcome for the community following completion of AWARE2ALL.

6.4.2. IPR Management in AWARE2ALL

6.4.2.1. IPR audits

AWARE2ALL will actively monitor the creation of IPR during the lifetime of the project. As part of this process, Results which are both jointly and individually owned will be identified. Proposals for the division of share of such results and the base conditions for their exploitation were made by the project team.

These proposals will be made in line with the conditions set out in the Consortium Agreement and in function of the IPR audits conducted. In order to perform these audits, an Intellectual Property Officer (IPO) will be involved. The role involves the survey and reports of Foreground Intellectual Property. The IPO assists the Coordinator in the IP Management. Nevertheless, each partner is responsible to apply the knowledge protection measures.

The different sections of the IPR audit are described in the tables below, including background and results registration.

Table 13 Information to be included per Background IPR item

Title	<i>Name of Background IPR</i>
Organisation	<i>Owner of background IPR</i>
Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Software</i>• <i>Hardware</i>• <i>Firmware</i>• <i>Other (if Other, please specify:</i>

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Dataset (Text / Images/ Sounds/ Voices) - Database Content ○ Model Database (S.S.O)/ Model Web (S.S.O) ○ Database (aesthetic) Design / Web Design / Model Design ○ Scientific / Technical Information; ○ Inference engine / Knowledge base - Expert system (Artificial Intelligence) ○ Algorithm ○ Etc.)
Description	
Conditions and limitations for implementation	
Conditions and limitations for exploitation	

Table 14 Information to be included per Foreground IP item

Title of IPR	<i>Name of the Foreground IPR item</i>	
IPR Owner	<i>Owner of the Results</i>	
Jointly developed	<i>No/Yes (add names)</i>	
Classification	<i>As per classification in Background IPR List</i>	
Related Background	<i>From listed Background IPR items</i>	
Control of Third Owners Software, Hardware or IPR	Identification of Commercial Software and Licensor:	
	Identification of Open Source Software and Licensor:	
	Identification of commercial hardware:	
	Third Owner Intellectual Property Rights:	
Description		
Exploitation Potential	<i>Further Research</i> <i>Developing, creating and marketing a product/process</i> <i>Creating and providing a service</i>	

	<i>In Standardisation activities Others (Joint Venture, Spin-off, ...)</i>
Protection Plan	<i>Patent Utility model Industrial design Copyright Trademark Confidential information Other, specify</i>
Access Rights	<i>According to the GA and Section the CA, "access rights" means licenses and users rights to Background or Foreground given to beneficiaries of the project (Party or Parties) if it is Needed to enable those Parties to carry out their own work under the Project.</i>
Available Support (email, website, info)	
Registration date	
Modified by	
Version	

6.4.2.2. IPR Management Strategies

Among the diverse channels for IP management, patents, copyrights, trademarks, and geographical indications are the most used methods for IPR protection, which are discussed in more detail below. It is important to highlight that partners can also consider an IPR strategy based on open source, open licenses or sharing knowledge freely with the objective of fostering innovation and raising awareness on specific topics among the community

1. **Patents:** WIPO defines a patent as a legal right that gives the inventor exclusive control over his invention and allows him to decide whether and how the invention can be used by others. In exchange for this right, the inventor is required to disclose the technical details of his invention in the published patent specification.
2. **Copyright:** Original works such as literature, music, choreography, graphics, sound recordings, art, architecture and software are protected by copyright. The copyright owner has the exclusive right to modify, distribute, perform, create, display, and copy the work. Copyright protection exists by default at the moment the asset is created. Registration of a copyright is usually optional but gives the asset immediate rights in the event of infringement.
3. **Trademark:** Trademark protection is granted for a word, phrase, symbol, or design used to identify the source of a good or service. For a trademark to be protected, it must be unique and distinguishable from other marks on the market. Generally, trademarks are protected only if they are actively used, and rights in a trademark may be lost if it is

abandoned, becomes generic, or is improperly licensed or transferred without quality control or supervision by the trademark owner [4].

4. **Geographical indications:** Geographical indications and designations of origin are names given to products that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities, characteristics or a reputation that are mainly attributable to that origin. These designations usually include the name of the region or place from which the product originates [5].

6.5. AWARE2ALL expected results

A preliminary table with exploitable results and IP protection mechanisms is provided below (Table 15). At the end of the project, a Results Owner List (ROL) included in the final periodic report, due in M36, listing all items of knowledge relating to the work of the project (pre-existing know-how and results developed in the project), and making explicit for each item: the owner(s); the nature of the knowledge and its perceived potential for exploitation; the agreed status of the item concerning plans to use the knowledge in exploitation, or plans to disseminate it outside the consortium and measures required, or in place, to ensure protection of IPR for the item.

Table 15 AWARE2ALL Expected Results.

	AWARE2ALL KER	IPR holder	IP protection mechanisms
Passive safety systems	KER1 - Control algorithm considering occupants body motion and seating position information from interior monitoring system (out-of-position control)	ESI, THI, CERTH	Protect the IPR (trade secret) and explore strategies for exploitation (e.g., licensing or further services for clients).
Active safety systems	KER2 - Advanced active safety features including lane-change manoeuvres in emergency situations for crash avoidance	THI, TNO, TEC	Industry secret, potentially extended to other scenarios and conditions.
	KER3 - Advanced trajectory optimization algorithm for a wide range of driving conditions	TNO, THI, TEC	Confidential to the generator/owner of the foreground.
	KER4 - Fail-Operational strategies for DDT fallback functions	TEC	SW code protection or patent.
iHMI	KER5 - New strategies for transition of full-automated mode (L4) to driver's active intervention and vice versa	TNO	Confidential to the generator/owner of the foreground. May/will be further developed after the project.

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

	KER6 - New approaches to cognitive load and situation awareness for multimodal HMI design	IRTSX	Confidential to the generator/owner of the foreground
OMS	KER7 - Occupant detection sensors, software and modelling	GEST	Patent filing
	KER8 - New, or further developed algorithms to estimate driver situational awareness.	TNO	Confidential to the generator/owner of the foreground. Further developed after the project.
eHMI	KER9 - Algorithms HRUs identification and behavioural prediction	FICO	Trade secret, will be included in company's perception systems
	KER10 - AVAS for eHMI sound interface	CEA	Patent filing
	KER11 - eHMI based on light and projections in windows	FEKA	Patent filing

7. References

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8. Appendix 1

Project Branding

Logo

The main objective of AWARE2ALL is to address the new safety challenges posed by the introduction of HAVs¹ in mixed road traffic, through the development of inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI (interior and exterior) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety. For this reason, our logo represents a hug that embraces everyone.

An infinite graphic that represents this automotive new wave that is in continuous changing, a non-static knowledge, learning constantly from the society and its evolution, has been added. Also, the rainbow-colored infinity symbol represents the diversity of the autism spectrum as well as the greater neurodiversity movement:

Symbol

Symbol + Wordmark

Alternative version

The horizontal version is required when the space available is low and wide.

Exclusion area

Funded by
the European Union

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The exclusion area is the space around the logo which must remain free from other elements to ensure that the logo is not obscured.

Minimum size

The minimum size of the logo for printing purposes and for the web is shown below. Never change the proportions when resizing it.

Digital: 100px Width

Print: 1 cm Width

Digital: 170px Width

Print: 1,7 cm Width

Digital: 283px Width

Print: 2,8 cm Width

Funded by
the European Union

Incorrect logo usage

Do not stretch the logo. Be careful with proportions of our logo.

Don't change the colour palette. You have our colours in this book brand, so please, don't change the colours of the project logo.

Technical specifications of the logo

Colours

The project's colour palette is shown below. It consists of one base colour: Dark grey, and then some joyful colours are used: Purple, Turquoise, Yellow and Orange. This palette passed the colour-blind safety and acquired a proper contrast for WCAG rules for website design accessibility.

Placement on different backgrounds

Colour versions for dark or clear background and monocolour versions for colour background will be used.

Typography

Segoe UI typeface, or font family, has been standard for years in Office 365 for Windows. Considering that is the operating system predominant in AWARE2ALL, it has been chosen as the primary project font because of its wide availability. However, it is missing in the Office 365 for Mac version and partners using Mac are encouraged to use the following alternatives, as they are similar in fonts and sizes:

Lucida Grande is similar to Segoe UI and is preinstalled on all Macs (it's the default system font).

[Noto Sans](#) and [Open Sans](#) are Google Font alternatives for Segoe UI.

Segoe UI is a Sans Serif and display font easy for reading in a screen or printable documents.

Segoe UI

The following guidelines provide standards for creating office documents and other forms of corporate texts using the Segoe UI font. The guidelines will help to give documents a more uniform appearance throughout the project.

Information about on minimum/maximum sizes will allow flexibility for varying document sizes.

AWARE2ALL_Headline Title

Heading

SEGOE UI

26 pt #0293B0

It should be used sparingly for impact; avoid overuse. Headline Title is also used for display text and labels.

AWARE2ALL_Headline01

Heading 01

Segoe UI

18 pt #525674

Used for titles when the use of Headline isn't appropriate, or used in conjunction with headline as project's style for standfirsts and callouts.

AWARE2ALL_Headline02

Heading 02

Segoe UI underlined

16 pt #525674

Headline 3 (H3)

Heading 03

Segoe UI

14 pt #525674

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Standard Text	Segoe UI regular for body copy
Segoe UI Light 11 pt #525674	For increased legibility, Segoe UI Regular is reserved for use in body copy and captions. Bold is used for subheads and callouts within body copy.
Quotes Segoe UI Light Italic 11 pt #525674	<i>"Coming together is the beginning. Keeping together is progress. Working together is success"</i> <i>Henry Ford</i>
Footnotes and captions Segoe UI Light 9 pt #525674	¹ Reference A footnote is a reference, explanation, or comment placed below the main text on a printed page. Footnotes will be identified in the text by a numeral.
Hyperlink Segoe UI Light 11 pt #0293B0	Link
Bullet Point 1 Symbol ●□ #0293B0 Bullet Point 2 Symbol ◦ #0293B0 Bullet Point 3 Symbol - Black	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bullet Point 1<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Bullet Point 2<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bullet Point 3

Office templates

Word

For Word files, two types of templates are available:

- Deliverable template
- Minutes of meeting template

DELIVERABLE TITLE

Deliverable subtitle

MEETING NAME

Location: [Location]
Date: [Date]
Time: [Time]
Called by: [Name + Organisation]

Attendance

[List attendees, Name + Organisation]

Agenda

1. Agenda Item / Presenter Name
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.

Meeting Notes

Details discussed during the meeting.

Action Items

Action	Assigned to	Due Date

Power Point

Prefixed style is available for various text & picture slides, timelines and contacts. This template will be used for all the project presentations.

Style guide

List of acronyms used in AWARE2ALL

Participant organization name (short name)	Acronym
FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES	VICOM
TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE INGOLSTADT	THI
ALTRAN INNOVACION, SL	CAP
ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH
NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK	TNO
FICOSA ADAS, S.L.	FICO
COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES	CEA
FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TEC
DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV	DLR

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

FEKA OTOMOTIV MAMULLERI SANAYI VE TICARET ANONIM SIRKETI	FEKA
NATIONAL ELECTRIC VEHICLE SWEDEN AB	NEVS
gestigon GmbH	GEST
INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE TECHNOLOGIQUE SYSTEMX	IRTSX
SYRMIA LLC Novi Sad	SYR
ESI SOFTWARE PAM SYSTEM INTERNATIONAL PSI	ESI
HUMANETICS EUROPE GMBH	HUM

Abbreviation	
Work Package	WP

Format Recommendations

Headings

Differentiate levels of headings using different sizes – check 3. Typography

Paragraphing

Use simple line spacing between paragraphs, with 6 points of spacing forward and backward between each paragraph.

Spelling

Use the British English spelling of words.

Use suffix -ise/-yse/-isation not -ize/-yze/-ization

Ensure that British English variants of words such as defence, labour, colour, analyse, organisation, archaeology, etc. are used.

Spellings in quoted material and book and article titles should not be changed.

Abbreviations are acceptable in parentheses, footnotes, tables, captions, use of abbreviations should be consistent both within and between chapters.

References

When inserting a figure or a table in a document, always use “[Insert caption](#)” option and use the labels “Table” and “Figure”.

Use the “Cross-reference” option to mention the caption in the text.

Cross-References

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

In-text cross-references should consist only of a chapter/title number or a caption with number.

Bold

Use bold to emphasise some details (deadline, name) in the text to stand it out.

Punctuation which follows bold text should not itself be bold (unless the whole sentence is in bold type)

Italics

Use italics for foreign words and phrases embedded within your text (i.e. inter alia).

Use italics for titles of books and journals if they are a complete published work (Risk society).

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Don't use full stops after any abbreviations, contractions or acronyms

If numerous abbreviations or acronyms are used, please provide a list of them. If there is no List in the document, explain unusual abbreviations/acronyms on their first occurrence, for example, HAV (Highly Automated Vehicle).

Avoid unnecessary abbreviations (e.g. those that will only be used once in the document).

Do not use the full point after contractions, i.e. abbreviations that include the first and last letter of the word (e.g. Dr, St, Ltd). The exception to this rule is "no." for number.

If there is no list, spell acronyms out in full the first time it is mentioned, with the acronym following in brackets; thereafter, use the acronym alone: Autonomous Vehicles Readiness Index (AVRI).

Citations

The APA (American Psychological Association) style will be used for citations when necessary.

In text:

The obstacles for HAVs introduction in the market mainly come from safety and human factors concerns¹.

Bibliography:

¹Favarò, F. M., Nader, N., Eurich, S. O., Tripp, M., & Varadaraju, N. (2017). Examining accident reports involving autonomous vehicles in California. PLoS one, 12(9), e0184952.

Information on EU funding

All beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding must use the EU emblem in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes and contribute to the visibility of the EU on the ground. The logo can be found in https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en.

Recipients of EU funding have a general obligation to communicate and raise EU visibility. An important obligation in this context is the correct and prominent display of the EU emblem, in combination with a simple funding statement, mentioning the EU support.

The EU emblem is the single most important visual brand used to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of EU funding. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight EU support.

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars and information material such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc. in electronic form via traditional or social media), as well as any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant, must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement.

All information related to the Operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding in the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027 can be found in https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/3192a0ef-6bda-4e1a-81ca-65ade2ffad73_en?filename=eu_emblem_rules.pdf

9. Appendix 2

AWARE2ALL

Project Summary

Safety systems and human-machine interfaces oriented to diverse population towards future scenarios with increasing share of highly automated vehicles

THE PROJECT IN A NUTSHELL

Topic: HORIZON-CL5 2022 D6-01-02: Reliable occupant protection technologies and HMI solutions to ensure the safety of highly automated vehicles

Type of action: Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Coordinator: VICOMTECH

Start date: 01/11/2022

End date: 31/10/2025

Duration: 36 months

Budget: 7,999,817.50 €

Project number: 101076868

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076868>

- 1 vicomech
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- 3 Cogniscience
- 4 TNO
- 5 TNO
- 6 TNO
- 7 TNO
- 8 tecnolo
- 9 TNO
- 10 TNO
- 11 NEVS
- 12 greatigan
- 13 Syntex
- 14 SYRMIA
- 15 SYRMIA
- 16 HUMANETICS

MOTIVATION

In 2020 someone died on European roads every 25 minutes.

EU-wide, around 70% of road fatalities in urban areas involve vulnerable road users.

There is increased safety risk across age groups (children, adults, older adults), types of impairment (e.g., sensory, developmental, cognitive, physical impairments), and among users of mobility devices.

Most user studies in the field of automotive safety are conducted with predominantly young male and technologically educated participants.

AWARE2ALL will effectively address the changes in road safety derived from the introduction of Autonomous Vehicles, putting special focus on underrepresented populations (female, elderly, sensorial or physical disabilities, cultural minorities, low digital abilities) to ensure that results provide safety to any (type of) occupant and HRU¹.

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AWARE2ALL acronym
It is an acronym including diversity of the AWARE2ALL project

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of AWARE2ALL is to address the new safety challenges posed by the introduction of HAVs² in mixed road traffic, through the development of inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI³ (internal and external) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety.

- **OBJ 1:** Definition and prioritisation of relevant Use Cases.
- **OBJ 2:** Develop one virtual prototype of passive safety (D1), addressing the variety of possible occupant postures and orientations and taking a large diversity of occupants into account.
- **OBJ 3:** Develop two active safety physical prototypes (D2, D3) to ensure that the vehicle is able to anticipate hazardous situations and act proactively, considering that a driver is not available (D2) and situations with driver available (D3).
- **OBJ 4:** Development of a hybrid (virtual and physical) prototype (D3) of iHMI⁴ that will adapt, dynamically, the required bi-directional interaction with the driver/occupants.
- **OBJ 5:** Extension of the current ODD⁵ definition by including occupant/driver state definition.
- **OBJ 6:** Develop an eHMI⁶ physical prototype (D4) for effective communication and interaction with diverse HRU¹.
- **OBJ 7:** Develop innovative testing methods and tools for performance assessment of AWARE2ALL safety and HMI³ solutions.

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Project summary 4

CONCEPT

AWARE2ALL concept is based on three pillars:

- P1 – Integral safety**, to guarantee always that even if a crash is unavoidable, the severity is minimised.
- P2 – Interior situation awareness**, to ensure that occupant alertness is adequate for the current driving mode.
- P3 – Exterior situation awareness**, to inform road users about the vehicles state and intentions.

Pillars table
Summary table of the 3 project pillars

Funded by the European Union

Project summary 5

WORKPLAN

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Project summary 6

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

EXPECTED RESULTS

Systems developed in AWARE2ALL will be implemented in a total of four demonstrators:

DEMO 1 (D1)

Passive Safety virtual prototype

Occupant protection (restraint systems) + new vehicle interior

DEMO 2 (D2)

Active safety – no driver available (shuttle) physical prototype

AEB⁷ + Fallback / Emergency maneuvering

DEMO 3 (D3)

iHMI⁵, OMS⁸ and Active safety – driver available hybrid prototype

Handover / Handback + iHMI⁴ + OMS⁸

DEMO 4 (D4)

eHMI⁶ physical prototype

Perception system and eHMI⁶

Simulation

V2X⁹

Vehicle

Driving Simulation

VRUs¹⁰

Project summary 7

CONTACTS

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Project summary 8

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